

PHILOSOPHY

DEVELOPMENT OF JOURNALISM IN THE PHILOSOPHICAL SPACE

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Abstract

The article analyzes the emergence and development of journalism in the philosophical space. Journalism in the philosophical space has historically manifested itself in various modifications, such as philosophical journalism, philosophical journalism, philosophical magazine, media philosophy, visual philosophy. This topic has not yet found a sufficiently comprehensive study both in philosophy and in the works of media analysts, although the relevance of such a study is undoubted, since new realities have emerged: such as the information society, media reality, media philosophy, etc.

Keywords: philosophy, journalism, mass media, philosophical journalism.

The philosophical analysis of journalism was actualized in the late twentieth and early twenty-first centuries. This circumstance is due, first of all, to the fact that journalism has begun to touch almost all spheres of human and social life. There is no sphere of society where journalism does not intervene. Thanks to this, it has a radical impact on the social, professional, educational, political, and spiritual spheres of life. Journalism has also touched upon such a sphere of spiritual production as philosophy. Philosophy and journalism are socio-cultural phenomena, but their connection began only at the end of the eighteenth century. The origins of this connection are born with the appearance of the first printed media in Europe - newspapers and magazines. The relationship between philosophy and journalism becomes part of the discourse on its philosophical understanding. This discourse is historical and dynamic. Journalism today is a part of the mass media poly-system, multifunctional institutions of society, such as the press, television, radio, and the Internet, i.e., there are various types of journalism. Hence, it is necessary to determine their correlation, connection with philosophy, and the role of journalism in the philosophical space. This aspect is the purpose of the article. So far, there are no special substantiated studies on this issue, although two international conferences have already been held at St. Petersburg University on media philosophy (2007) and the historical development of philosophical journalism (2010). The theoretical foundations for analyzing journalism in the philosophical space are presented in various aspects in the works of such well-known philosophers and media analysts as M. McLuhan, J. Brodriard, D. Rushkoff, F. Fukuyama, L. Lesh, L. Pento, G. Pocheptsov, I. Mykhailyn, V. Mironov, A. Carmine, V. Fedotova, V. Podorozha, V. Dubrovsky, V. Savchuk, M. Shlemkevych, O. Sobol, M. Luhmann, I. Pavlyk, M. Emery, L. Zamaleev, A. Ivanenko, V. Proleyev, I. Smirnov, M. Stepanov, and others.

It should be noted that in the works of media analysts, and above all on the pages of the International

Journal "Gazeta", it is said that the theory of journalism, the understanding of journalism proposed in the early twentieth century by F. Siebert, T. Peterson and W. Schramm in their work "Four Theories of the Press" cannot satisfy modern researchers and be relevant to modern reality. Recent scholarly works, both foreign and domestic, emphasize the understanding of journalism as a component of communication studies, a means of communication and communication. It was this point in the analysis of philosophical journalism that was emphasized at the conference at St. Petersburg University in November 2010.

Journalism in the philosophical space manifests itself as a philosophical journal, as a means of professional communication. One cannot but agree with the point of view of Russian researchers that the philosophical journal is becoming one of the important institutions capable of ensuring both the communication of the philosophical community and the interaction of philosophy with other areas of social and humanitarian knowledge [1, p. 227].

Philosophical journalism and philosophical journals have become a kind of being of philosophy since their inception, just as the novel became such a being in the second half of the nineteenth century.

In his article "Philosophical Journalism" in the journal "Sociologos" in 1997, the French philosopher L. Pento noted that journalism as a component of the media interferes with such an esoteric sphere as philosophical production, appropriates a special form of competence, although it seems to claim secondary roles, chooses stars, topics, and titles. Journalists seem to only describe what is happening before their eyes and without their participation. This invasion is not limited to the frontier, it concerns the impact on the entire field of spiritual production [8]. The author raises a very important problem: allegedly, not explicit interference in philosophy actually leads to a weakening of internal control, philosophy is interpreted in such categories as hybridity, parasitism, and mingling, and philosophy

loses its identity. L. Pento's opinion should be emphasized that nowadays there is a situation where philosophical journalism is no longer perceived as marginal, it is intended to become part of the usual attributes of the career of a new mandarin, trying to put philosophy under control, falsifying the image of philosophy and philosopher [8]. There is a deprofessionalization of philosophy, as emphasized by postmodernists. Thus, R. Rorty stated in his work "Philosophy and the Future" that there is no need to care about the purity of philosophy [9]. Ortega y "Gasset" drew attention to the deprofessionalization of philosophy even earlier, noting that philosophers are becoming everything: politicians, teachers, writers, researchers, but not philosophers [6]. According to M. Luhmann, R. Rorty, Beck, and L. Pento, philosophical production in the modern world is becoming a commodity, a component of a single world - the commodity world. In this sense, philosophical journalism also becomes a kind of commodity. This circumstance changes the functions of both journalism and philosophy, which is facilitated by the information society.

In today's society, journalism is ready to advertise anything: cars, laundry detergents and clothes, hygiene products, the human body, and even concepts. The philosophy of "revealing simple truths," which is now being polarized in numerous white books by Paulo Coelho, Antoine de Couattier, and many other "interpreters of life," suggests that everything can be sold or bought. And even get a lot of money for it. Not the least role in this is played by the mass media, which distributes, informs and provides the average user with new discoveries today. Like a horoscope that advises to refrain from conflicts today, it creates an everyday philosophy for itself. Almost everyone should realize that philosophy is good and a sign of education. Philosophy is for the masses. Philosophy is for everyone's home. In general, the knowledge that is created and accumulated by a few dissolves among millions. It's like a dish that a professional chef worked to create, and which the whole family enjoys after putting it in the microwave.

This is the influence of magazines on philosophy. This is what Yas Persian called the ability to communicate. This can be considered positive or negative, condemned by highly specialized conservative philosophers, or, on the contrary, proclaimed a geometric progression in the development of philosophy by those who seek to spread it over as many territories as possible. But despite the strong defenses of journalism, or rather, its opening of borders for everything innovative, which, like a snowball, merges into something big and influential, philosophy also has something to contribute to the postulates. At the moment, we can talk about the creation of so-called intellectual journalism - philosophical journalism. Those experts in words and their work who have gone beyond the dryness of news reports and the objectivity of analytical articles can safely refer their publications to this type of journalism. Unlike philosophers, who give up the simple in favor of a complex and deeper comprehension of things, they tackle the problems of everyday life that require subjective thought. Many university philosophy graduates have the ability and desire to try their hand at the press,

and no fewer journalists prefer philosophical essays. Freed from the constraints and requirements of the journalistic genre, they create their own concepts of seeing the world, combined with professional experience and knowledge of life. Perhaps they are even more productive than philosophers themselves, taking advantage of the many masks that journalists have to wear in their daily work. But on the other hand, this can lead to ambiguity in their views, variability of opinion, and instability of position.

The new turn in philosophical journalism was almost universally welcomed by young professionals. For example, an electronic literary and philosophical almanac of students of the Moscow State University's journalism faculty is available on the Internet, and they characterized it with the following apt statement: "Journalism is a curved line, while philosophy is a set of segments, each of which ends with a large number of original segments." To decipher their thought, we can say that journalism is a planned path characterized by the typical features of all genres: relevance, informativeness and efficiency. It never compromises these postulates, only sometimes changing the vector of its direction depending on the surrounding circumstances. Philosophy creates many thoughts, many concepts, which can either be in the same plane or never meet. And each new thought is at the same time a space for new disputes, new views, and, as a result, new branches (segments) of the philosophical current.

Philosophy is currently in an ambiguous position. Secular literature? Intellectual writing that divides people into "those who are in the know" and "those who are not"? Is it possible that the popularization of journalism only stimulates its development? The influence of philosophy on the fourth power can be evaluated positively - commentators have learned to think with their own worldview in mind. Philosophical journalism = literary culture? Many questions, and not only these, will arise for those who discover the ability to philosophize in life. How to solve them is up to both the journalist and the philosopher, because each of them already has the right to think subjectively.

The emergence of media reality presents multiple images, a new configuration of philosophical journalism. Not only professionals become the subjects of philosophical journalism, it is open to specialists in various fields, and it takes on the expression of a kind of intellectual game. According to L. Pento, philosophical journalism is becoming a cultural form par excellence, thanks to which mediators, people who cross borders and make transitions, whether they are journalists, writers or university professors, contribute to making free circulation in the intellectual field collectively acceptable [8, p. 30-35]. This is the meaning of philosophical journalism as a free means of communication, both professional and cultural, and public in general. In today's philosophical situation, a philosophical journal acquires the character of intercultural communication.

Philosophy has always been interested in the relationships between people, their interaction and mutual influence, not just communication in itself, but its role in education, science, and culture. Philosophical jour-

nalism is a very important tool in this process, as evidenced by the dynamics of philosophical journal publishing in the world in the twentieth century.

At the beginning of the First World War of 1914-1918, more than 40 philosophical journals were published in the world; during the war, the publication of many philosophical journals was interrupted, and some ceased to be published. In 1919-1939, 57 new philosophical journals appeared in Germany, Italy, France, and the United States; they began to be published in China, Australia, and India; specialized philosophical journals on the logic and methodology of science appeared ["Erkenntnis" (Lpz., 1930-1940); "Philosophy of Science" (Bat., since 1934); "Theoria" (Goteborg, since 1935)].

During the Second World War (1939-1945), 21 philosophical journals ceased to be published. New philosophical journals were created mainly in the United States. In the postwar years, the number of journals increased: in 1945-1950, 37 new philosophical journals were created, in 1950 - about 50, in 1951-1960 - also about 50, in 1960-1966, about 40 new journals began to be published. During this period, philosophical journals appeared in a number of Latin American countries (Argentina, Chile, Brazil, Mexico, Ecuador), Pakistan, and India; there was a further specialization of philosophical journals in the history of philosophy, aesthetics, methodological problems of social sciences, ethics, and logic; abstract philosophical journals and new international philosophical journals were created. The main trend in the development of philosophical journalism is the doubling of their total number in 15-20 years (in 1850 - 4, 1870 - 9, 1890 - 19, 1910 - 38, 1930 - 58, 1950 - 97, 1970 - about 200).

At the beginning of the XXI century philosophical journals are published in Russian - 15, in English in Australia - 1, England - 8, the Netherlands - 2, Norway - 1, the USA - 22, international philosophical journals - 7, in German - 1, in Germany - 19, in French in Belgium, France, Canada - 15, as well as 7 international ones, in Spanish - 1, in Italian - 28, philosophical journals are published in Bulgaria - 2, Brazil - 2, Poland - 4, Romania - 1, Finland - 1, Estonia - 1. As for Ukraine, "The Ulrich's international" listed only one philosophical journal in 1970 [3]. But the situation with philosophical journalism has changed. Philosophical journals are published in almost all universities of the country, although, unfortunately, there is no list of them, since most of them are published at the expense of teachers and graduate students. Why do we have this situation? According to S. Proleyev, who stated this in his article "The Purpose of a Philosophy Journal in the Mirror of Statistics," the manifestation of this state of philosophical journalism in Ukraine is the rapid decline of philosophy and related disciplines in the structure of university education. We have a situation of a kind of "shagreen skin" that is shrinking in size so rapidly in the course of the national university situation that the entire twenty-five-century-old respectable philosophical tradition, this intellectual core of European history, will soon be left in Ukrainian universities as a small patch, suitable only for covering up for the current situation, as even savages do. It seems that even today,

Ukrainian educators and university administrators do not get rid of this thing only out of shyness, not seeing any other useful, educational role for philosophy [7, p. 138].

It should be noted that this is almost the only comprehensive article in recent years, both at the end of the twentieth century and not at the beginning of the twenty-first century, not only about the fate of the Ukrainian philosophical academic journal "Philosophical Thought" but also about the fate of philosophy. This idea is also present in V. Anashvili's interview with the Russian Journal. He emphasizes that without a number of qualified journals of multiple "orientations" and several "national" humanities journals, we will face a scientific turning point [4, p.7]. Analyzing the state of philosophical journalism in Russia, he draws a very pessimistic conclusion: the Philosophy Faculty of Moscow State University publishes the "Bulletin of the Philosophy Faculty" with a circulation of 6300 copies, and this is Moscow State University - it is a world university. And its journal should be appropriate, large-scale, if not international. "Questions of Philosophy" and "Philosophical Sciences" have long since lost the nerve of modern humanitarian journalism, gloomily returning to the style and themes of long gone times [4, p. 10].

The authoritative Philosopher's Index, which has existed since 1967 and is updated every three months, still does not include Russian journals and yearbooks. According to Yu. Sineokoya, this can be explained by the publishers' disinterest, not always reflected by the emphasis on self-sufficiency, hermeticity, and absence in the global professional dialogue on equal terms [10, p. 115]. Ukrainian philosophical periodicals are also absent from the index. The reasons for its absence are similar to those of the Russian ones.

The position of S. Proleiev, V. Anashvili, and Y. Syneokoya is shared by V. Porus, who believes that there is a contradiction between the many thousands of professional philosophers and the small number of philosophical journals, their number is pathetic and cannot be compared with the situation in some European countries. He makes a rather harsh statement that even this "insignificant" journal production by modern standards is filled with compilation and abstract descriptions, against which high-quality works become an exception. The philosophical journal becomes a means of producing "complicated" personnel who lose their purpose. That is why, according to V. Porus, our journals cannot be called avant-garde.

Analyzing philosophical journalism, it should be emphasized that in the information society it is a component of the mass media. N. Luhmann drew attention to this fact, emphasizing that the concept of mass media should cover all social institutions that use technical means of dissemination to disseminate messages, that the products of mass media are newspapers, magazines, photocopies, etc., but not manuscripts written in dictation in the Middle Ages, and not public speeches and stories in our time. Distribution technology has played an important role in the process of separating the mass media system, just as money played a role in relation to the economy [5, p.15].

The modern information reality has made significant changes in the theory and practice of journalism and philosophical understanding of communication. Philosophical journalism is becoming more and more the subject of scientific analysis due to a number of socio-cultural circumstances. The understanding of the very phenomenon of "journalism" has changed. It is becoming a structural element of the mass media.

Philosophical journalism is one of the professional means of communication and should be classified as a scientific type, since philosophy has the status of a science. At the same time, philosophical journalism can be interpreted as a kind of corporate culture. From this perspective, there is no analysis of philosophical journalism, although it is quite relevant. It is relevant because it raises the question: is philosophical journalism only and only for specialists, or is it changing its status and becoming public? The analysis of scientific publications (a rather small number) shows that the interpretation of philosophical journalism has two directions: classical and post-classical, tradition/innovation. While the classical trend in philosophical journalism is associated with its emergence in the bosom of German philosophy, the post-classical trend is associated with the emergence of post-classical philosophical thought, and above all, postmodernism.

Modern media technologies are changing the configuration of philosophical journalism. At the beginning of its emergence in European culture in the late eighteenth and early nineteenth centuries, philosophical journalism existed as mono-journalism, only as a magazine, as a book. This model of a philosophical journal was embodied in the late nineteenth century in the "Philosophical Three Monthly" published at Kyiv University by Professor V. Kozlov. It was the first philosophical journal to appear at that time in both Ukraine and Russia. V. Kozlov's journal is an analog of the philosophical journals published by F. Schelling in Germany, which became the birthplace of philosophical journalism. It was this country that initiated journalism as the existence of philosophy. F. Schelling synthesized philosophy and journalism, and he can undoubtedly be considered the first philosopher-journalist. The beginning of journalism in Ukraine is associated with the Kharkiv Imperial University in the first quarter of the nineteenth century. I. Mykhailyn, analyzing the first magazines in Slobozhanshchyna and Ukraine, proves their important feature: the essence of philosophical topics. This applies to such first journals as Democritus, Ukrainian Journal, and the journal Faith and Reason made a significant contribution to the philosophical space. It was the first philosophical journal in the Russian Empire. An interesting and rather fruitful opinion in this regard is that of the Russian researcher L.F. Zamaleev, who noted that without the support of journalism in the first half of the nineteenth century, the formation of philosophy would not have taken place in the Russian Empire, and that, in the words of G. Florovsky, there would not have been a philosophical "icebreaker". The periodicals of the twelfth century discussed the meaning of philosophy as wisdom, and created philosophical movements and trends. The whole color of the

university professors is organized into newspapers and magazines [2].

In this context, the opinion of the famous Ukrainian philosopher and journalist M. Shlemkevych is worthy of attention. In 1948, he published an article "Organ of Public Opinion (Ideas for Philosophical Journalism)" in the foreign journal "Problems", in which he proves that the worldview of the Ukrainian nation was built and created by publicists and journalists, not philosophers, which is typical for Germany and France, where it was formed in academies and universities since the eighteenth century [11].

Media reality presents multiple images, a new configuration of philosophical journalism. It is becoming a kind of media philosophy, presenting itself as an online magazine, a blog, a visual image, etc. Technology is becoming the main factor that not only determines the development of new configurations of philosophical journalism, but also the means of its manifestation. As a result of this situation, scientific contacts and scientific cooperation overcome national and regional borders and become communication without borders. Intercultural scientific communication and intercultural scientific interaction are taking place. According to Yu. Sineoka, since 1980 philosophical periodicals have increasingly played the role of moderator of philosophical discourse. This applies to both experimentation with the identification of philosophy by appealing to the language of politics, art, psychotherapy, etc. and the expansion of the space of philosophy itself, the construction of new disciplines [10, p. 135].

Thus, in modern conditions, philosophical journalism is an important element of mass media. It is one of the means of scientific communication that presents a new configuration in the information society. Philosophical journalism presents itself as a book, as an online magazine, changing the means of ineffective communication, turning any problem that worries people into a commodity and entertainment in the global communication space, setting a new configuration of philosophy, acting as an alternative to its classical academic image.

References

1. Demin M.R., Mochalova I.N. Philosophical journal as a space of professional communication (Demin M.R., Mochalova I.N. // Vestnik St. Petersburg University. -Vol. 2. Philosophy. - 2010. - № 4, - c. 226-258.
2. Zamaleev L.F. Philosophy and Russian Journalism (Zamaleev L.F.) // Vestnik MSU, Journalism Series. 2004. - No. 4, - Moscow, pp. 48-54.
3. Electronic resource. - Access mode: <http://www.philifo.org.him>.
4. Interview of V. Anashvili, editor of the Logos magazine, to the correspondent of the Russian Journal. 19.05.06: [electronic resource]. - Access mode: <http://www.russ.ru/publish>.
5. Luhmann N. Reality of mass media / N. Luhmann; [translated from German by A.Y. Antonovsky]. - Moscow: Praxin, 2005. - 256 p.

6. Ortega y Gasset, J. The Rise of the Masses (Ortega y Gasset, Jose) // Essays on Literature and Art. Collection. - Moscow, 1991. 112 c.

7. Proleyev S. The purpose of the philosophical journal in the mirror of statistics / S. Proleyev // Philosophical thought. 2010 - № 6. - pp. 137-142.

8. Pento L. Philosophical journalism / L. Pento; [translated from the French by E.D. Voznesenskaya] // Sociologos. - Moscow: Institute of Experimental Sociology, 1997. - P. 30-56.

9. Rorty R. Philosophy and the Future / R. Rorty; [translated from English by T.N. Blagova] // Voprosy filosofii. - 1994. - № 6. - C. 29-34

10. Sineokaya Y.V. Experience of comparing domestic and Western philosophy (on the pages of philosophical journals) / Y.V. Sineokaya. Sineokaya // Philosophical Sciences. - 2007. - № 12. - M. 114-135.

11. Shlemkevych M. Organ of public opinion. (Ideas for philosophical journalism). (Nikolai Shlemkevych) // Problems. - 1949. part II. -Berlin.

12. Ulrich's international: periodicals directory. - 1971. - C. 1278-1289.